

Study of Blue green algae from Cotton fields of Nyahali village of Nandurbar district of Maharashtra state

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Abstract

Algal cultures have been used in various morphological, physiological, biochemical and genetic researches. A Re-evaluation of taxonomic delimitations of many forms, polymorphisms, antibiotic resistance, variability, cytology, genetic and mutation as been made possible with the help of authentic algal cultures. Algal cultures also enabled the remarkable progress in our knowledge of life cycles of algae. Algal cultures have greatly contributed to many physiological discoveries. Number of scientist carried out the culturing method to make algal culture by using bacteriological techniques. Famintzin (1871) used some nutrients which are used by angiosperm. The Current is based on Blue green algal study on cotton fields of Nyahali village and finds various variety for lab culture study were taken with scientific classifications.

Key words: Algae culture, Blue green algae, Nandubar and Cotton fields.

Introduction

Since ancient time during the evolution of earth, algae supposed to be evolved as first autotrophic plants. The algae grow under natural condition as mixed communities. For studying them man have started collecting them in natural form and culture them in laboratory condition. The culture needs suitable environmental condition and nutritional requirement.

Culture of algae in the laboratory becomes necessary for studying algae for a number of purposes like:

- 1) Cytological study
- 2) Life histories
- 3) Morphological study
- 4) Genetic study

- 5) Definition of species
- 6) Physiological studies like nutrition, metabolism, photosynthesis, respiration etc.

For study of the algae the culture must be pure i.e., presence of only one species in culture vessels free from other organism. They are also called as unialgae, unispecific culture. However according to Pringshem (1926, 1946) various 6 types of cultures are described like preservation, crude, enrichment, pure, absolute, clone culture.

While studying them some of the blue green algae of soil have shown agronomical importance. De (1939), Venkatraman (1981), Singh, 1961; Watanabe et al. 1951). Based on pure cultures studies some myxophycean members show ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen Singh (1961) and increase the crop yield. The lichen also shows various types of blue green algae along with fungi. The algae are also along in reclamation of waste water.

Soil algae refer to the sum total of various ecological groups, viz., terrestrial algae growing abundantly (as crusts or films) at the soil surface, aquatic or terrestrial forms growing at the surface of permanently damp soil and soil algae proper, found below the soil surface. Soil algae play an important part in various soil processes. Marathe has recently considerable aggregation of the loose unbound particles in the soil by the growth of certain blue green algae which seems to be largely due to the polysaccharides secreted by them.

Blue green algae occur widely, particularly in the tropics. Although recurrent combinations of algae species appeared, particularly in comparable habitats, the generalization that practically all cultivated soils support rather abundant nitrogen fixing blue green algal flora may not be universally applicable.

Now man knows that blue green algae are with capacity to fix atmospheric nitrogen which can increase the yield of the crops like rice. Therefore in the present study we try to study the presence of blue green algae in the soil of the farmers who are growing various cash crops of the region like cotton. In Dhule and Nandurbar district we can see that the cotton is one of the most valuable cash crops, which is very important for the livelihood of the farmers because it gives

more money to the farmers (Khan PA and Patil MB 2016). The farmers of this area are not more aware with the use of blue green algae as biofertilizers (Patil MB and Khan PA 2017).

Therefore to make them aware we selected this topic. Therefore firstly we have started studying the soil samples from various places whether the blue green algae are present in their agricultural field or not. For that purpose we have collected soil samples from the agricultural fields from village like Nyahali. By studying the soil samples we will inform the farmer. Whether his fields are having the potential for growth of blue green algae and make him aware of which type of blue green algae are present in the soil.

The above study will help the farmer while using various types of Azo-Rhizo cultures present in market while growing the cash crops like cotton, tur, gram, and banana. "The time is past when cultures serve as an end in themselves, allowing the taxonomist to amuse himself by preserving for a short time the strain he likes."(Wrutz 1964).

Materials and Methods

To culture the algae the soil samples are to be collected and they are grown in liquid cultures in conical flask. It is done as follows:

a) Collection of Soil Sample:

The soil sample which is collected is air dried soil. The soil samples were collected from the agricultural fields from all the peripheral, middle and central position of the field 1 kg sample was collected from each place about to 17 places were selected from the field and surface soil sample may have more possibility for presence of algal spores. The soil samples were thoroughly mixed and from the 17 kg sample was retained for inoculation. Soil sample is collected in different polythene bag. Sample was inoculated in each liquid medium and solid medium. 1gm each in 250ml of liquid medium.

Requirements for Culturing:

- i. Culture vessels
- ii. Media
- iii. Light, Temperature
- iv. Soil

i. Culture vessels:

Usually glassware of high quality glass like Pyrex or corning brands are used for preventing chemical contamination of media during sterilization and later on. Glassware may be washed or cleaned in particular ways as required. They are normally washed first with a detergent and later with concentrated solution, tap water or distilled water. Sterilized non absorbent cotton is used as stoppers.

ii. Media:

One type of media is used in culturing of algae:

a) Liquid media**Chemicals:**

Chemicals used should be of highest purity and of a standard company. Utmost accuracy in weighing the chemicals has to be taken. Some algae can grow in cultures of inorganic chemicals too.

Water:

When water is to be used in medium it should be non toxic. Tap water and distilled water may contain heavy metals. Double distilled water is preferable. Deionized water is required for the study of trace elements.

pH:

pH of the culture medium is one of the important factors for the healthy growth of cultures. Blue green algae grow well in pH- 7.5 to 9. It is therefore important to use media which are well buffered. Selection of nitrogen source is important factor in deciding the pH of the culture. In the present study we have used pH 5.0, 5.5, 6.0, 6.5, 7.0, 7.5. Liquid culture. We try to study the response of the soil sample to above pH range.

Light:

At one time cultures were advised to be kept near the window only as it was thought that light from window is absolutely essential. It is now known that there should be usually provided for alternating with dark period.

Temperature:

A temperature between 20°C-30°C is recommended for many algae. Blue green algae grow well at temperature 30°C-32°C.

Preparation of medium:

Myer's C medium is used for the preparation of medium.

Liquid Medium:

KNO ₃	- 1.0gm
K ₂ HPO ₄	- 1.0gm
Ca (NO ₃).7H ₂ O	- 0.025gm
MgSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	- 0.25gm
Na citrate	- 0.165gm
FeSO ₄ .7H ₂ O	- 0.02gm
A5 solution	- 1ml
pH	- 5, 5.5, 6, 6.5, 7, 7.5
D.W	- 1000ml

Sterilization:

The medium which is prepared is sterilized with the help of autoclave. Sterilization is made to avoid contamination. Due to sterilization the medium get sterilized and bacterial free. Glassware also sterilized before the culture process.

Hot air oven is used to sterilize the glassware. In oven sterilization achieved normally by maintaining internal temperature 120°C for 30 minutes. Autoclave is most

efficient and common instrument used for sterilization of solid and liquid media. Adjust the pressure up to 15 lbs.

After sterilization of liquid medium, it is poured in 6 different conical flask and they are adjust in 6 different pH values ranges from 5-7.5. These conical flask mouths are closed with non absorbent cotton and again it is sterilized in hot air oven.

Inoculation: The inoculation of sample was done in laminar air flow in the vicinity of spirit lamp. Utmost care was taken to avoid contamination. Take 1gm soil and inoculate it in liquid and solid media. After inoculation the soil sample in the conical flasks containing liquid medium are kept under diffused light. Keep conical flask under diffused light near the window of the room for 15-20 weeks.

The culture was incubated in diffused sunlight in the month of September 2011 to January 2012. The cultures was given fresh medium frequently at the interval of 15 days at room temperature about 28°C-33°C.

Preservation of Culture:

After the growth of the algae the organisms were preserved in (F.A.A) Formalin Acetic Acid solution and maintained. The culture was regularly observed for growth of algae. The cultures are preserved in plastic bottle.

Result at pH – 5.0:

1) *Chroococcus micrococcus* (Kutz.) Rabenh.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus: - *Chroococcus*

Species: - *micrococcus* (kutz) Rabenh.

Thallus mucilaginous, somewhat broad, yellowish brown, more or less dilated; cells spherical, 2-4 together, also single, 25-50 μ diam., with sheath 30-80 μ diam., sheath thick, colourless, lamellated.

2) *Chroococcus tenax* (Kirchn.) Hieron.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Chroococcus*

Species: - *tenax* (kirchn.) Hieron

Cells mostly in groups of 2-4, sometimes 8-16, blue green or olive coloured, without sheath 16-24 μ diam., with sheath 20-26 μ in diam., sheath colourless or yellow to brown, very distinctly lamellate.

3) *Aphanocapsa koordersi* Strom.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Aphanocapsa*

Species: - *koordersi* strom.

Colony spherical, dull green to blue green, 2-3mm. in diam., cells loosely arranged or in groups of four, spherical, 2.2-2.8 μ in diam..

Result at pH – 5.5:

1) *Gleocapsa montana*_Kutz.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Gleocapsa*

Species: - *montana* kutz.

Thallus amorphous, broad, mucilaginous, pale yellowish, or light green in colour; cells spherical or subspherical, with sheath 4-10 μ broad and without sheath 2-5 μ broad, diam., single or two together in a colony, colony 13-28 μ broad; sheath lamellated, colourless, outer lamellae diffluent; contents more or less opaque, homogenous, finely granular, pale blue-green.

2) *Chroococcus montanus* Hansgirg.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Chroococcus*

Species: - *montanus* Hansgirg.

Thallus slimy, gelatinous, brownish or blackish brown; cells 5-6 μ seldom, 3-9 μ diam., single or 2-4, seldom more in irregular groups of 19-25 μ in diam., rarely upto 30 μ diam., colonial sheath lamellose.

Result at pH – 6.0:

1) *Gleocapsa montana* Kutz.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Gleocapsa*

Species: - *montana* kutz.

Thallus amorphous, broad, mucilaginous, pale yellowish, or light green in colour; cells spherical or subspherical, with sheath 4-10 μ broad and without sheath 2-5 μ broad, diam., single or two together in a colony, colony 13-28 μ broad; sheath lamellated, colourless, outer lamellae diffluent; contents more or less opaque, homogenous, finely granular, pale blue-green.

2) *Chroococcus minutus* (Kutz.) Nag.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Chroococcus*

Species: - *minutus* (kutz.) Nag.

Cells spherical or oblong, single or in groups of 2-4, light blue-green, with sheath 6-15 μ diam., and without sheath 4-10 μ diam., colonies 10-13 x 15-20 μ ; sheath not lamellated, colourless.

Result at pH -6.5:

1) *Chlorococcum turgidus* Nag.

Classification:-

Division: - Chlorophyta

Class: - Chlorophyceae

Order:- Chlorococcales

Family:- Chlorococcaceae

Genus:- *Chlorococcum*

Species: - *turgidus*

Thallus amorphous, broad, mucilaginous, pale yellowish, or light green in colour; cells spherical or subspherical, with sheath 4-10 μ broad and without sheath 2-5 μ broad, diam., single or two together in a colony, colony 13-28 μ broad; sheath lamellated, colourless, outer lamellae diffluent; contents more or less opaque, homogenous, finely granular, pale blue-green.

2) *Gleotheca samoensis* Wille.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Gleothece*

Species: - *samoensis_wille*.

Cells ellipsoidal, without sheath 4-5 μ broad, 8 μ long, cells yellowish or bluish green, in round colonies, often many uniting, mostly 2-4 in common envelope, envelope, colourless, unlamellated.

3) *Anabaena variabilis* Kutzing ex Born.et Flah.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Nostocales

Family:- Nostocaceae

Genus:- *Anabaena*

Species: - *variabilis* kutzing ex Born.et Flah

Thallus gelatinous, dark green; trichome without any sheath, flexuous, 4-6 μ broad, more often 4.2-5 μ broad slightly constricted at the cross-walls, end-cells colonial, obtuse; cells barrel shaped, 2.5-6 μ long.

Result at pH – 7.0:

1) *Chlorococcum turgidus* Nag.

Classification:-

Division: - Chlorophyta

Class: - Chlorophyceae

Order:- Chlorococcales

Family:- Chlorococcaceae

Genus:- *Chlorococcum*

Species:- *turgidus*

Thallus amorphous, broad, mucilaginous, pale yellowish, or light green in colour; cells spherical or subspherical, with sheath 4-10 μ broad and without sheath 2-5 μ broad, diam., single or two together in a colony, colony 13-28 μ broad; sheath lamellated, colourless, outer lamellae diffluent; contents more or less opaque, homogenous, finely granular, pale blue-green.

2) *Chroococcus montanus* Hansgirg.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Chroococcus*

Species: - *montanus* Hansgirg.

Thallus slimy, gelatinous, brownish or blackish brown; cells 5-6 μ seldom, 3-9 μ diam., single or 2-4, seldom more in irregular groups of 19-25 μ in diam., rarely upto 30 μ diam., colonial sheath lamellose.

3) *Anabaena variabilis* Kutzing ex Born.et Flah.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Nostocales

Family:- Nostocaceae

Genus:- *Anabaena*

Species: - *variabilis* kutzing ex Born.et Flah

Thallus gelatinous, dark green; trichome without any sheath, flexuous, 4-6 μ broad, more often 4.2-5 μ broad slightly constricted at the cross-walls, end-cells colonial, obtuse; cells barrel shaped, 2.5-6 μ long.

Result at pH – 7.5:

1) *Gleocapsa montana* Kutz.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Gleocapsa*

Species: - *montana* kutz.

Thallus amorphous, broad, mucilaginous, pale yellowish, or light green in colour; cells spherical or subspherical, with sheath 4-10 μ broad and without sheath 2-5 μ broad, diam., single or two together in a colony, colony 13-28 μ broad; sheath lamellated, colourless, outer lamellae diffluent; contents more or less opaque, homogenous, finely granular, pale blue-green.

2) *Gleocapsa livida* (Carm.) kutz.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Chroococcales

Family:- Chroococcaceae

Genus:- *Gleocapsa*

Species: - *livida* (carm.)Kutz.

Thallus mucilaginous, first rounded or lobed, later expanded, hyaline, greenish to olive brown in colour; cells small, with sheath 6-8 μ diam., and without sheath 3-4 μ diam., in colonies of 16-94 μ diam., sheath light bluish, hyaline; contents densely bluish green.

3) *Gleotrichia raciborskii* Woloszynska.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Nostocales

Family:- Rivulariaceae

Genus:- *Gleotrichia*

Species: - *raciborskii* Woloszynska.

Thallus spherical, soft, 1-5mm diam.; trichome 7-8 μ broad, ending in a long hair, with hair up to 800 μ long; sheath at the base lamellated, dull brown; cells at the base of the trichome, shorter than broad, higher up as long as broad, or longer, pale blue green; heterocysts spherical, 5-6.4 μ broad.

4) *Phormidium anomala* Rao, C.B.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Nostocales

Family:- Oscillatoriaceae

Genus:- *Phormidium*

Species: - *anomala* Rao, C.B.

Thallus thick expanded, soft, mucilaginous, deep blue-green, 3-6mm thick; trichome sub-parallel of uniform width, 8-10 μ broad without constrictions at the cross-walls; sheath thin, colourless, not stained by chloro-zinc-iodide, persistent or dissolved; cells disc-shaped, much broader than long, 0.8-1.2 μ long; end cells bluntly rounded without cap or calyptra.

5) *Phormidium pachydermaticum* Fremy.

Classification:-

Division: - Cyanophyta

Class: - Cyanophyceae

Order:- Nostocales

Family:- Oscillatoriaceae

Genus:- *Phormidium*

Species: - *pachydermaticum* Fremy.

Thallus outer surface dull blue-green, inside brown; filaments 6-10 μ broad, straight or undulating; sheath at first thin, later thick, irregularly lamellated, lamellae short, irregularly disposed, outside more or less rough, trichome blue green, 5-6 μ broad, not constricted at the cross-walls, ends straight, not attenuated, not capstate; cells nearly quadrate or up to $\frac{1}{2}$ as long as broad, septa not granulated; end cells slightly convex or obtuse conical, with slightly thickened outer membrane.

Discussion

As we know soil algae play an important role in various soil processes. Many algal spores are present in agricultural field. Large algal population occurs on fertile cultivated soils, a great proportion of which is composed of nitrogen fixing blue green algal forms. The agricultural and economical importance depends on the capacity of certain species to carry out both photosynthesis and nitrogen fixation.

Present study throughout the investigation which is carried out with Myer's medium in liquid and solid form. The response of the soil samples was studied to different pH as 5, 5.5, 6, 6.5, 7, and 7.5. We found that there is less number of algal spores present in that agricultural field. To know which type of algal spores are present in that agricultural field algal culture is done in laboratory. We observed Cyanophycean members are present in that agricultural field. They are listed below:

1. Blue green algae found in pH-5.
 - i. *Chroococcus macrococcus* (Kutz) Rabenh
 - ii. *Chroococcus tenex* (Kirchn.) Hieron
 - iii. *Aphanocapsa koordersi* strom.

2. Blue green algae found in pH-5.5
 - i. *Gleocapsa montana* Kutz
 - ii. *Chroococcus montanus* Hansgirg

3. Blue green algae found in pH-6.0
 - i. *Gleocapsa montana* Kutz
 - ii. *Chroococcus minutus* (Kutz.) Nag

4. Blue green algae found in pH-6.5
 - i. *Chlorococcum turgidus* Nag.
 - ii. *Gleotheca samoensis* Wille
 - iii. *Anabaena variabilis* Kutzing ex Born.et Flah

5. Blue green algae found in pH-7.0
 - i. *Chlorococcum turgidus* Nag.
 - ii. *Chroococcus montanus* Hansgirg
 - iii. *Anabaena variabilis* Kutzing ex Born.et Flah

6. Blue green algae found in pH-7.5
 - i. *Gleocapsa montana* Kutz
 - ii. *Gleocapsa livida* (Carm.) Kutz
 - iii. *Gleotrichia raciborskii* Woloszynska
 - iv. *Phormidium anomala* Roa, C.B.
 - v. *Phormidium pachydermatium* Fremy.

From pH-5 to pH-7.5, we have found 13 types of algae in total we got less no. of algae in pH-5 and maximum no. of algae in pH-7.5. The above study indicates that the high pH favors the growth of blue green algae. As we go from acidic pH to alkaline pH, we found that the growth of algae is more and the organisms found more in number.

We have found less number of algal members in particular agricultural fields. The reason may be excess use of insecticides and pesticides which kills the algal flora of the soils. The soil may be infertile. Therefore we will inform those farmers whether their fields are having the potential for the growth of blue green algae and make aware them which type of blue green algae are present in their soil.

We can suggest to farmer to use different agricultural techniques to increase the crop population. They can use Azo-rhizo culture present in market while growing the different cash crop. In Azo-rhizo cultural technique the seeds are treated with Azo-rhizo treatment. These treated seeds are sown in agricultural field to increase the crop population as well as the algal flora of the soil will grow on increasing year by year. It will help in nitrogen fixation and help to reduce the cost of production by spending less money on nitrogen containing fertilizer like urea.

In India there are subsidized fertilizers which are available to the farmers. These farmers use excess fertilizers that are more than needed quantity. With the help of the above recommendation the quality of soil will increase year after year and the soil will remain fertile for upcoming years. The soil will not become salty and remains good for cultivation of various cash crops like cotton, gram, tur, groundnut, etc.

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